

Fairness in Healthcare and Beyond—A Survey

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Abstract: This article presents an extensive literature review on the importance of fairness in society, science, the world of work and leisure, with a focus on healthcare. Depending on the application area, fairness criteria and metrics play a major role in evaluation, classification, and allocation. Different approaches to a general definition of algorithmic fairness for individuals or groups are considered, and their measures from the perspective of the concerned sciences and requirements for the decision-making processes are also formulated. There are many reasons for the lack of fairness: inadequate data quality or low model performance, differences in understanding, competing standards, inappropriate measures in selection, classification and decision-making, lack of accuracy or performance of algorithms paired with insufficient communication, interaction or collaboration of stakeholders. The requirements are illustrated using the example of medical risk prediction tools, e.g., the individual and familial risk for the occurrence of pathogenic variants in BRCA1 (BRest CAncer 1) or BRCA2 genes with impact on early breast cancer (BC) and ovarian cancer (OC) disease, and the 5-year risk that an individual with ocular hypertension will develop Primary Open Angle Glaucoma (POAG), the leading global cause of irreversible blindness.

Keywords: Trust, (algorithmic) fairness, assessment, discrimination, measure, risk prevention, medical tool, explainable artificial intelligence.

Categories: H.4, J.2, J.3, J.4

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1 Introduction

Fairness is an overarching value and can be understood as responding to individual characteristics without disadvantaging others—a responsiveness to individual characteristics that accompanies people throughout their lives, in the areas of education, leisure and sport, in dealings with state institutions, with banks and insurance companies, and in the medical field [IOC, 21]. The problem of fair assignment to a group of people with similar characteristics—fair distribution of resources, places, jobs, or services—arises in all areas of everyday life and shows the dilemma of different fairness measures. Well-known examples are competing metrics and ethical values in the allocation of the limited number of hospital beds during the COVID-19 pandemic [Zohny, 22], the division into groups of similar athletes at the Paralympics, and the distribution of mandates among the parties in parliamentary elections, in which contradictory definitions of individual and group fairness and different electoral systems lead to various procedures and algorithms with different outcomes. What is special about this concept is that

individuals and groups, societies, and authorities have their own ideas about how fairness and related concepts such as discrimination, disadvantage, and exclusion can be measured and prevented, depending on the respective areas. And that these metrics can collide with the rules and standards that apply in the context of fairness.

In this paper, we deal with a selection of in our opinion most relevant publications and accompanying literature, start with a section on terminology, and introduce the following concepts (cf. [Jui, 24]).

- A *protected attribute* (PA), such as origin/ethnicity, gender, professional group membership or religion, creates a partition of a population (in relation to place and time) whose subsets are equal in terms of application-specific performance in the sense of fairness. The term *sensitive attribute* is also used in the literature.
- *Group/individual fairness* aims to treat groups/individuals with PAs similarly with similar outcomes when applying an algorithm or decision procedure.
- A *privileged value* of a PA refers to a group or individual that has a systematic advantage.
- *Bias prevents fairness*. Lack of fairness can be equated with undesirable biases that systematically favour privileged groups/individuals and systematically disadvantage unprivileged groups/individuals.
- A *fairness metric* allows the quantification of undesirable biases in training data for groups, individuals, or models based on fairness criteria.
- A *bias reduction algorithm* is a method for reducing undesirable biases in data sets, algorithms or models.
- *Fairness, or absence of bias*, means that criteria, measurements, classifications in the decision-making processes, and the interpretation of results do not disadvantage individuals or certain groups or subgroups.
- *Reliability* means that consistent and repeatable results are achieved when measuring quality criteria and that uncertainty is considered.
- While *aleatory* uncertainty refers to the statistical variability of the outcome, epistemic uncertainty captures the uncertainty that arises from a lack of knowledge. Statistical variables, such as mean values and variances, are important when compiling cohorts; epistemic uncertainty arises when determining the first occurrence of a disease or disease patterns in the family.
- *Validity*, or degree of evidence, concerns assurances that decision-making processes and classifications are carried out in accordance with the specified rules, quality criteria and their metrics, and that the results are described accurately [RVF, 24].

With the scientific progress of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), parallel worlds, e.g., the metaverse populated with digital twins, and new research questions arise, such as algorithmic fairness, fairness in ML, fairness in governance, new financial institutions and technologies in blockchain, and fairness in healthcare for individuals and groups with various risks.

Access to equitable medical care and confidence in medical services, doctors, and nursing staff are crucial for an aging population. Given the widespread adoption of online advice, prevention, and risk prediction tools, it is imperative to prioritize an evaluation of reliability, validity, and trust through metrics [Weber, 24].

AI is a collective term for technologies that support and enhance human abilities in hearing and seeing, analysing, deciding, communicating, and acting. It is based on the comprehensive digitalization of systems and processes (cognitive systems and their digital twins) and requires complex computer-based system architectures with their

interfaces. It makes sense to differentiate between partial, complete, and extended AI systems and AI-based applications, depending on how extensively human properties are enabled: learning, thinking, reasoning, interaction, cooperation, and communication with native languages, facial expressions, and gestures between humans and AI systems.

AI in multi-modal human-machine interaction requires large language models (LLM) and, currently, huge distributed computing resources. The LMMs Med-PaLM and Med-Palm2 are available at <https://sites.research.google/med-palm/> and designed to provide high-quality answers to medical questions. Ethical use and the exclusion of misinformation are important requirements that must be met.

“AI should be explainable, comprehensible, and meet specified quality standards, and interpretability methods help to restrict discrimination and enhance fairness in machine learning models” [Linaradatos, 21].

This requires international agreements on domain-based criteria and metrics, procedures for validating results, and, if necessary, adapting AI systems through learning in cooperation with experts. Results, predictions, recommendations, and the general use of AI-based assistance systems in the medical sector, in particular, need interdisciplinary evaluation, assessment, and cooperative decision-making when it comes to the specific treatment of patients’ preventive or follow-up care. As is known from game theory or multi-objective optimization, it cannot be excluded that not all criteria can be met equally well and that there should be procedures for finding compromises or defining a balance.

In contrast to logistic regression models for risk prevention, models using Dempster-Shafer theory (DST) represent a direct explanatory relationship between disease patterns and assignment to risk classes [Luther, 22] [Gillner, 23]. A calculator for the 5-year risk of developing primary open angle glaucoma is presented in [Baloian, 24].

The DST starts with a finite frame of discernment $\Omega := \{A_1, \dots, A_n\}$ describing a system or a model and its states. It combines evidence from different sources and provides a measure of confidence that a given event occurs, a random variable X , now a belief variable, belongs to a certain set, e.g., an interval $[x_{Bel}, x_{Pl}]$. X is characterized by its basic probability assignment (BPA), subsets with masses $m(A) > 0$, $A \in 2^\Omega$, which, for example, represent the proband’s or relatives’ personal risk and experts’ risk estimates. The result is given by the lower and upper limits (belief and plausibility) for the probability of a subset of the frame of discernment, $Bel(X) := \sum_{H \subseteq X} m(H)$, $Pl(X) := \sum_{H \cap X \neq \emptyset} m(H)$.

Notice that $m(\cdot): 2^\Omega \rightarrow [0,1]$, $m(\emptyset) = 0$; the mass of the empty set (impossible event) is zero, $\sum_{X \in 2^\Omega} m(X) = 1$, and $F(m) := \{X \in 2^\Omega, m(X) > 0\}$ denotes the set of all focal elements.

Using Dempster’s Rule with $m_{1,2}(X) := \sum_{X_1 \cap X_2 = X, X_1, X_2 \in 2^\Omega} m_1(X_1)m_2(X_2)$, a combined BPA with $m_{DS}(\emptyset) := 0$, $m_{DS}(X) := m_{1,2}(X) / (1 - m_{1,2}(\emptyset))$, $X \neq \emptyset$ is obtained.

In the cases of epistemic uncertainty, intervals represent the available (bounded) data better than machine numbers. They can be propagated from input to output of a static or dynamic model using interval analysis (IA) [Moore, 09]. Interval arithmetic is described in [IEEE, 15]; roughly speaking it transfers the arithmetic operations of machine numbers to machine intervals and calculates the result intervals using the lower and upper limits of the operands and rounding operations. In [Auer, 10], a brief

introduction to the fundamentals of the DST and its interval extension DSI is given. The authors describe the main features of the DSI TOOLBOX and discuss several basic usage examples.

[Chen, 23] assesses concepts of fairness and discrimination in the digital transformation of public health, the application of AI and ML algorithms in the medical field, and their impact on patient health from the perspective of the stakeholders, patients, and experts involved. The authors discuss ethical and legal considerations such as data protection, responsibility, accountability, transparency, and explainability in AI, as is also addressed in [Kumar, 24].

Of course, all these modern development processes are characterized by economic interests; the systems use existing knowledge, and the companies involved use marketable solutions, data, and metadata that are subject to digital rights management. In that respect, these processes are not conflict-free or fair, and moderation or mediation is required in the event of conflicting interpretations of the results of AI systems.

People who are disadvantaged in terms of access to hardware and software, devices and the tools themselves, and people with cognitive impairments can also be the subject of discrimination. In the following, we will look at the concept of (algorithmic) fairness from the perspective of different scientific disciplines.

To identify relevant literature in the field, we conducted several document searches in various international databases using the keywords ‘explainable’, ‘artificial intelligence’, ‘algorithmic fairness’, ‘bias’, ‘discrimination’, ‘health tool’, ‘reliability’, ‘validity’, ‘trust’, and ‘risk prevention’. which returned more than 100 hits in the categories of journal articles/reviews, conference papers, and (chapters in) books published between 2018 and 2025 from the fields of engineering, computer science, and social sciences. At this stage, we will discuss important reviews that can serve as initial information on the topic. A detailed analysis of the selection and classification of the relevant references is presented in Section 4.

[Bellamy, 19] presents a Python toolkit for algorithmic fairness, AI Fairness 360 (AIF360) at <https://github.com/ibm/aif360>, an extensible architecture, released under an Apache v2.0 license. It includes a comprehensive set of fairness metrics for datasets and models, explanations for these metrics, and algorithms to mitigate bias in datasets and models. The tool provides an interface to seven popular datasets concerning census, income, credit, recidivism, marketing, and three versions of Medical Expenditure Panel Surveys (MEPS), a set of large-scale surveys of families and individuals.

[Chen, 23] also provides a comprehensive overview of the fairness issues in AI systems through practical applications, e.g., social administration, and focuses on bias analysis and fairness training. The paper mentions 10 different types of biases and their measurements (cf. Tables 2–4). Assessment of fairness across the individual stages of an AI-supported decision-making process is worth to be considered in this context, starting with careful planning. In the medical field, this begins with the selection of cohorts, the consideration of databases from different national or international health organizations regarding standards and similar studies, and the handling of epistemic uncertainty, the lack of data, their unconscious or conscious exclusion, the quality of the calibration of the models, and their stability or sensitivity. Here individual fairness means that similar patients receive equivalent treatments, which requires similarity metrics.

A ‘similarity’ definition is missing in [Chen, 23] and could be based on various distance notions and measurements applied to points, sets, text, or images.

Classification uses statistical evaluation metrics based on quality criteria such as accuracy and efficiency, statistical analysis and metrics such as F-score, precision, recall, sensitivity and specificity, AUC (area under the curve), ROC (receiver operating characteristic), or, in the best case, an individual assignment to non-overlapping groups of patients.

Low-performance models lead to classification errors, e.g., when assigning people to risk groups, which have a direct negative impact on those affected. Fairness must be evaluated alongside accuracy and requires predictive models to not unfairly disadvantage specific demographic groups. To evaluate fairness in prediction models for the development of psychosis and functional outcome, criteria and measures are needed.

The authors of [El Azab, 23] and [Şahin, 24] evaluated relevant fairness aspects for the demographic attributes 'gender' and 'educational attainment' and compared them with the fairness in clinicians' judgments. In general, it is preferable to use models that, when validated, result in the correct classification for each individual in the cohort or furnish at least correct lower or upper limits when it comes to risk prediction.

Educational bias was present in algorithmic and clinicians' predictions, assuming more favourable outcomes for individuals with higher educational levels (years of education). [Tirendi, 23] considers normative recommendations in the form of a statement on 'Fairness of AI Recommendations in Healthcare' (FAIR), which summarizes best practices. With a comprehensive exploration of bias, fairness, transparency, and accountability, it guides readers through the intricate *web of ethical considerations*.

However, it should be noted that the risk of disease may well depend on gender or origin, as is shown by the occurrence of harmful gene mutations in ethnic groups with founder effects or patients with triple-negative breast cancer status [Luther, 22] or the more frequent occurrence of normal-tension glaucoma in females [Zukerman, 21, ref. 80].

[Linardatos, 21] lists, analyses and compares interpretability methods for explaining deep learning models (such as black box models), compiles tables that link explainable AI (XAI) technologies with application companions, models and methods, fairness issues, and also names unsuitable approaches. "Systems whose decisions are not easily interpretable are difficult to trust, especially in areas such as healthcare or self-driving cars, where moral and fairness issues naturally arise." Several techniques for controlling discrimination and removing the bias from machine learning models are presented.

In Section 2, we will discuss aspects of algorithmic fairness and fairness metrics from the perspective of the concerned sciences, give some examples of online risk prediction models, and briefly characterize them. Section 3 deals with biases in medical tools for risk prevention. A detailed literature analysis is presented in Section 4. A further section 5 presents a case study on fairness in the use of medical tools and proposes a score-based metric. In healthcare, careful preliminary considerations are required for a fair assessment approach. A comparison of the results of risk calculators and related studies is possible only if similar patient groups are medically treated according to the same procedures and similar protocols, and if the measurements use the same procedures, model parameters, and concern overlapping periods. For example, for glaucoma screening, measurements are undertaken for both eyes several times at regular intervals under defined conditions using the same procedures. A statistical model adjustment and a calibration have been carried out. The final section presents our conclusions and further work.

This article is an updated and extended version of the contribution [Harutyunyan, 24] presented at the CODASSCA meeting on Collaborative Technologies and Data Science in Smart City Applications in Yerevan, Armenia, October 3–6 [Hajian, 24].

2 A Critical Debate on General Algorithm Fairness

Algorithmic fairness is the subject of an investigation to ensure that algorithms and their results are unbiased and that they do not discriminate against individuals or groups regarding protected attributes. Since algorithms generally refer to models or processes, specific design and implementation requirements are needed to prevent discrimination.

In the context of medical risk tools, fairness metrics for the underlying models and algorithms are of particular interest. A score-based tool metric may be part of a complex audit procedure and is made up of individual numerical values (scores) that are assigned according to a specific description of requirements. They allow the assessment of the risk model, the factors and classes, the patient groups and individual risks, the tool (software, middleware, and hardware), and the data management. An evaluation of the interaction between the participants also concerns patient care and communication with experts, the cooperation of the groups involved, and is supplemented by process validation over appropriate periods of time, which checks the assignment of patients to (risk) groups and corrects it, if necessary. Validation also compares these results with the findings from other models, patient groups, and organizations. In this article, we limit ourselves to online medical tools and their interfaces, to databases, patients, and experts. There are various reasons for this.

Requirements such as correct input of medical parameters in the specified arithmetic formats must be supported and checked by the implemented model for correctness and completeness in the background. Methods for determination change over time, are only convertible or comparable with each other to a limited extent, or, in the case of repeatedly collected health parameters in a given period, must be transparently averaged and assigned to a specified value range, which ultimately means that reliable operation and use of the tools should take place preferably in the presence of a competent person [Baloian, 24].

The paper [Loftus, 18] deals with current approaches to algorithmic fairness using causal reasoning and summarizes its most important findings. There is a fundamental disagreement on the way to a generally valid definition of algorithmic fairness. Are algorithmic decision-making procedures fair if they always make similar decisions for similar individuals, or if they make advantageous decisions for all groups at the same rate? As a consistent rule, criteria from different value systems cannot be fulfilled simultaneously. In addition, algorithms use data and are part of one of many models. Thus, disadvantages can also arise in data collection and selection and depend on the scope of use, and this applies equally to input and results. As a conclusion, the authors state that “machine learning algorithms can unwittingly perpetuate or create discriminatory decisions that are biased against certain individuals.”

[Mitchell, 21] considers algorithmic fairness, lists a catalogue of fairness definitions, and delivers a compact reference guide to the decisions, assumptions, and fairness considerations for (equal) prediction measures and prediction-based decision-making.

Binary decision: 1) Index people p_i by $i = 1, \dots, n$. 2) Persons have features, variables, or inputs $v_i \in V$ known at decision time. 3) Sensitive variables v_i, a_i (e.g., PA

race, gender, or class), and other variables x_i , writing $v_i = (a_i, x_i)$. The person's outcome is denoted by y_i . 4) Then a binary decision d_i for each person is defined. "Decisions are restricted to be functions of variables known at decision time, $\delta: V \rightarrow \{0,1\}$, where $d_i = \delta(v_i)$. Random variables $V, Y, D = \delta(V)$ are defined as the values of a person randomly drawn from the population. In prediction-based decisions, decisions are made based on a prediction of an outcome, y_i , that is unknown at decision time. Specifically, decisions are made by first estimating the conditional probability $P[Y=1|V=v_i]$. The decision system does not know the true conditional probability; instead, it uses an estimate." More details are given in the paper [Mitchell, 21].

Subsets of advantaged and disadvantaged subgroups defined by their predictions and outcomes are described by a confusion matrix, which illustrates match and mismatch, and is used in this article for relationships between Y , the outcome, and D , the decision. In this prediction-based decision setup, when $Y = D$, the correct decision has been made. Equality among groups of each of these measures defines mathematical notions of fairness.

Green's paper [Green, 22] presents a literature review on algorithmic fairness, which concludes with the following words: "Although no mathematical definition of algorithmic fairness fully encapsulates the philosophical notion of fairness or justice, each definition captures a normatively desirable principle."

Instead of treating fairness as a technical attribute of algorithms, the author introduces *substantive* algorithmic fairness that focuses on whether and how algorithms can promote equity in the sense of equal opportunities and equal treatment in practice.

Whereas *formal algorithmic fairness* is a decision-making process that aligns with formal equality (which emphasizes equal treatment for individuals based on their attributes or behaviour at a particular decision), *substantive algorithmic fairness* is based on theories of substantive equality from law and philosophy and focuses on whether and how algorithms can promote equity in practice: "First, reduce the upstream (social) disparities that feed into decision-making processes. Second, reduce the downstream harms that result for those judged unfavourably within the decision-making process."

In his Figure 2, the author develops and comments on a flowchart for the implementation of substantive algorithmic fairness. The process starts at the beginning of the flowchart by addressing discrimination or inequality in a particular decision-making process. This feeds into the considerations of substantive equality, with a focus on relational and structural inequalities.

If neither relational nor structural concerns are prominent (i.e., the answers to both questions in step 1 are 'No'), then the process moves on to formal equality considerations. In this case, the questions are similar to those that already exist in the context of formal algorithmic fairness. In the other case, in step 2, identify potential reforms; possibilities for reforming social hierarchies are considered, and decision-making structures are adapted; and in step 3, consider roles for algorithms; algorithms are used where possible to improve relational and institutional reforms. Substantive algorithmic fairness is therefore more an extension of the methodology of algorithmic fairness than a complete rejection of formal algorithmic fairness.

[Petersen, 23] assesses the fairness of risk score models in classification systems and comes to the following conclusions: The fairness of risk score models is a function of the epistemic value (E)—successes, progresses, created knowledge, understanding or true beliefs—they provide to different groups. It should be evaluated independently of

any subsequent decision-making process. A de-biased calibration error metric allows us to empirically quantify the EV. A risk score model is fair if it provides a similar EV to all groups of interest, defined by one or more sensitive attributes. Subject ranking based purely on predicted risks is often unfair.

[Weinkauff, 24] states that “algorithmic fairness shares in the basic properties of fairness, but it also differentiates itself from the ethical concept of fairness by focusing on the treatment of individuals and groups within the context of an AI/ML model.”

He recommends measures that can be applied to help achieve algorithmic fairness:

- Ensure that training data is balanced and representative of the population; the ground truth is objective.
- Ensure that features equally predict the target variable across groups.
- Set the threshold to a value that satisfies your fairness criteria.
- Use a separate threshold for each group.

In conclusion, as stated by the author, mathematical notions don’t address the ethical implications of the actual task an AI/ML model performs. Algorithmic fairness consists of multiple definitions that are generally incompatible; its results can be manipulated, and it cannot evaluate its effects.

The establishment of a generally valid metric for algorithmic fairness is controversial in the literature. Depending on the origin of the experts, various reasons are given for this, all of which are similar in that logical constructs and ethical maxims cannot be reconciled, as they are based on incompatible axioms or normative systems.

Particular difficulties also arise from the fact that there are extremely diverse approaches to the algorithmic classification of patients and their assignment to similar and dissimilar groups, which combine statistical measures or evidence-theoretical approaches such as DST or DSI to include epistemic uncertainty. Undoubtedly, the best solution is the most complicated one, namely, to consider an online risk prediction tool as fair if all patients have a disease progression that corresponds to the predicted risk group at the end of the period.

3 Biases in Medical Tools for Risk Prevention

Following [Ueda, 24], we will examine biases in healthcare, and especially in medical tools for risk prevention, that affect data selection cohorts, interaction with experts and their collaboration. From this perspective, we call a computer-based medical prediction tool fair if it meets the following requirements (cf. Figure 1).

a) The selection, composition, and follow-up of the cohorts used for modelling and validation of the prediction were accurately described, and the data were classified, processed, and made accessible according to international quality standards.

b) The modelling and result generation, including the theoretical foundations, technologies, architectures used and their validation, are described in comparison with existing tools and validated according to international quality criteria and quality measures, considering aleatory and epistemic uncertainty. To this end, it is necessary to follow the test subject group at least over the period of prediction, but preferably over a much longer period, and to adapt the tools for other test subject groups and further medical treatment, which particularly concerns progress in the clarification of genetic influences.

c) Fairness means that subgroups in the cohort that have special additional (unique) characteristics PA or whose numbers result in a higher uncertainty factor or require special treatment methods are not disfavoured [Siegfried, 22].

d) Preferably, validated realistic lower and upper limits are set for the risk classes; within those limits, a minimum standard of care is guaranteed [Auer, 21].

e) The treatment of clinical conditions is monitored by a panel of experts over the period established at the time of diagnosis and is adjusted accordingly as relevant new information becomes available [Kass, 21] [Kuchenbaecker, 17].

The discussion about the concept of fairness depends heavily on the professional world in which it is used: in business, it is about assessing the creditworthiness of a person or institution fairly; in selection interviews for a new job, it is about not disadvantaging applicants because they belong to a certain group.

Computer science is concerned with algorithmic fairness in decision-making problems, or the comprehensible use of AI and its results. Classification errors happen when assigning people to their risk groups due to lack of data and low-performance models, missing calibration, or uncertainty issues. Quality criteria and metrics guarantee the correct classification for each individual in the cohort, or at least correct and tight lower and upper bounds for risk prediction, while game theory is concerned with fair rules, utility functions, and equilibrium that are included in the decisions of individuals and the associated motivations for reward or punishment.

Figure 1: Biases in Healthcare Tools

Incompatibility of fairness criteria occurs when the interpretation of a positive or negative test is different in similar groups or depends on the value of the protected attribute [Paulus, 20]. The assessment of fairness across the individual stages of an AI-supported knowledge creating and decision-making process is also important from the perspective of the political institutions and described in the German Standardization Roadmap Artificial Intelligence in November 2020 at <https://www.dke.de>.

4 A Detailed Literature Analysis

In this section, different contexts of fairness and their biases are presented together with validity and reliability or trust, namely healthcare, learning and teaching, citizens and organizations, societal institutions and their structures, or a general assessment cycle in engineering in terms of modelling, simulation or implementation, and system validation. Another important topic is the measurement of trust in one’s own doctor.

4.1 Fairness Issues in Various Contexts and Application Areas

In this subsection, we examine the selected reference literature, classified by type, application area, and date of publication, in which fairness issues and the types of bias play a role (cf. Figure 2). Figure 3 lists the number of selected references by area of application AA and year Y of publication, including multiple assignments, and shows the increasing interest in the fairness debate in healthcare, explainable AI, and system design.

Figure 2: Types and application areas of fairness

Legend: O Overview, General Approaches; A Design, Modelling, and Simulation (Digital Twins), and Assessment Cycle in Engineering. Fairness, Trust, and Security in systems; B Fairness in AI: Foundation Models, Large Deep Learning Neural Networks, i.e., Large Language Models, and Generative AI; C Algorithmic Fairness and Quality of Algorithmic Decisions, Decision-Making, e.g., Classification, Benefits, and Services; D Citizen Score and COMPAS Software; E Healthcare, Risk Prevention, Trust in Doctors; F Trust in Individuals, Groups, Institutions, Societal and Scientific

Progress, Privacy, Security, Protection from Environmental and Technological Risks, etc. G Assessment in Learning and Teaching; H Fairness in Financial Services

General approaches. [Dominguez, 24] publishes a review of the literature on the harms and risks of foundation models and insights from critical data studies, science and technology studies, as well as environmental justice scholarship. We cite and comment on the identified 14 categories of risks in the context of foundation models as follows:

- Bias and societal prejudices, discrimination, and stereotypes
- Data, privacy, cyber-security, systemic social and economic risks, and
- Incorrect, incomplete, or misleading information; stereotypes; deliberately false information and propaganda
- Unreliable performance criteria of foundation models, i.e., validity, reliability, and sensitivity
- Legal and regulatory violations
- Environmental effects and ecological disruption
- Misuse of fairness metrics or classifiers—conflicting quality criteria
- Lock-in and opacity with impact on free decision-making processes
- Overdependency in human-computer interaction (HCI), overreliance of humans interacting with computer systems, interfaces, and technologies
- Value misalignment, bad or incorrect alignment of values in a business or other relation
- Environmental, extreme or catastrophic risks and harms.

Figure 3: Number of references to fairness by area of application AA and year Y of publication, including multiple assignments

[Wilkinson, 16] introduces the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Guiding Principles FAIR for scientific data management, a precondition for supporting knowledge discovery and innovation to improve the scholarly data infrastructure.

[Jui, 24] presents a classification of the methods used to solve different types of fairness issues: Based on different definitions of fairness in their context, different

biases in (training) data and decision models towards certain groups and a lack of predictive transparency are emphasized depending on the methodological approach.

De-biasing approaches to solve a multi-target problem, i.e., to satisfy different or multiple fairness descriptors for each (sensitive) attribute, can be divided into three categories. First, there are pre-processing algorithms, where the data is pre-processed before training to remove bias, with the goal that the learned classifier is fair. Secondly, there are in-processing algorithms that suggest changes to the software architectures or replacement of the algorithms at training time. Another approach is to use relaxations of fairness terms followed by a solution of a constrained optimization problem or additional regularization constraints. Finally, there are the post-processing algorithms, such as filtering the output of the classifier to ensure fairness [Padh, 21].

Fairness in systems, hardware, and software. [Ruiz-Martinez, 06] designs a fair and efficient protocol based on a trusted third party to make negotiation and contract signing processes secure and confidential. [Hafner, 09] proposes a new fair non-repudiation protocol for secure negotiation and contract signing and a reference security architecture that transposes the model of Software as a Service to the security domain and thereby realizes Security as a Service (SeAAS). [Dvořák, 10] introduces a new decision-making module that can generate representations of fair arbitrators/allocators in the form of a multi-terminal binary decision diagram (MTBDD) with nearly minimal cost and width.

Fairness in AI. Various types of fairness have been proposed in the literature, including group fairness, individual fairness, counterfactual fairness, and various forms of procedural fairness. “Counterfactual fairness states that a decision is fair towards an individual if it coincides with one that had been taken were the sensitive variable(s) different” [Caton, 24]. The survey paper [Ferrera, 23] provides a concise, comprehensive overview of fairness and bias in AI and addresses their sources, effects, and mitigation strategies in a matrix that illustrates the type of bias, a description, and examples. The following types are mentioned: data- and repository-based, model-based, algorithmic, decision-, classification-, and interaction-based fairness. Remedial strategies related to AI biases are then developed, leading to pre-processing and post-processing strategies, careful model selection, and a plea for responsible, explainable, and understandable AI. To avoid disadvantages for certain subgroups in classification, it is necessary to develop a classifier that does not discriminate against groups of people based on sensitive features. This can be done via regularization conditions or in a constrained optimization problem.

[Caton, 24] provides an overview of approaches and frameworks for increasing *fairness in ML*, more specifically in the areas of binary classification, regression, recommender systems and unsupervised learning, and divides them into pre-processing, in-processing and post-processing methods, which are further subdivided into 11 method areas. The article mentions that there are countless definitions and metrics to mathematically represent bias, fairness, and/or discrimination, and provides references or briefly refers to their definitions.

“Group-based fairness metrics compare groups based on predicted rates or expected outcomes by considering potential underlying differences between groups. Individual or counterfactual fairness metrics calculate distributions based on individual classification outcomes.” Abstract definitions for metrics are provided in [Caton 24, Section 3: Measuring Fairness and Bias].

Fairness in the society. China Citizen Score uses an algorithmic decision-making system that evaluates the citizen's professional and economic status in addition to civic behaviour, serves as the basis for decisions on lending and government grants, and also access to training, schools, universities or cultural events, but also housing or subsidies for renting or buying property, and supplements to health insurance or other benefits for the family. This involves an assessment of the individual's or family's financial resources to determine need or self-reliance and the extent to which benefits are provided on a credit basis. To standardize the decision-making process and comply with legal requirements, applicants and their families are assigned to groups or subgroups consisting of individuals or families who are similar in terms of professional, economic, and family status, following a classification and risk assessment (RA) [Zweig, 18].

The allocation based on the assessments and classifications made is carried out according to reliable and valid quality standards to meet the various requirements for fairness and to ensure that citizens in subgroups of comparable persons are also treated equally and discrimination is prevented. For people in a subgroup who differ in terms of sensitive attributes, such as ethical origin or genetic risks, measures are only fair and compatible if the consequential risks for them are the same.

Scoring systems are often used in the assessment, which makes the allocation dependent on whether a threshold value is exceeded or not. The quality of these scoring systems can be measured by the number of misallocations. A fairness metric therefore measures what is to pay for the incorrect subgroup allocations. The Correctional Offender Management Profiling for Alternative Sanctions (COMPAS) software is used to assess the risk to public safety in pretrial proceedings (PSPRA) and uses decision algorithms to assess the potential risk of recidivism. COMPAS includes two risk models, one for general offenses, one for felonies, and one for violent crimes [Räz, 22].

Fairness in healthcare. [Anderson, 25] identifies various approaches and methods introduced to achieve individual fairness and highlights how they can address biases in healthcare. The distance between two individuals a and b is quantified by a distance measure $m_a(a, b)$ satisfying $\sum_i |P(i|a) - P(i|b)| \leq m_a(a, b)$, where $P(i|\cdot)$ are the probabilities of the decision i for individuals a and b . Group fairness is based on parity of statistical metrics across groups that differ in a protected attribute.

Procedural justice refers to the perceived fairness of an organizational procedure (e.g., the perceived fairness of how healthcare delivery is organized). Further dimensions of organizational justice depend on the fair distribution of results or resources, causing no bias for groups or individuals over others, and trustful communication and cooperation between their physicians. The aim of the study on perceived organizational justice in healthcare [Pérez-Arechaederra, 14] was to develop and validate a measure of fairness for the patient. For this purpose, a survey study was conducted with two sample contexts—the USA and Spain—to enable cross-national validation of the scale in two versions. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were used to select the appropriate items for the final version of the instrument. The reliability of the measure and justice dimensions was assessed.

[Nelson, 19] deals with cancer incidence and mortality; discriminatory accuracy of RA tools for BRCA1/2 mutations; benefits and harms of RA; genetic counselling and testing; and risk-reducing interventions. The author is particularly concerned with the fair selection and monitoring of treatment options when patients have genetic risks.

Other relevant adverse effects of genetic tests, such as genetic discrimination and insurability, were not investigated.

[Chung, 21] introduces game-theoretic fairness and multi-party protocols in the case of leader election. By adopting an appropriate notion of approximate game-theoretic fairness, and under standard cryptographic assumptions, the authors achieve $(1-1/2^{\Theta(r)})$ -fairness in r rounds for $\Theta(\log \log n) \leq r \leq \Theta(\log n)$, where n denotes the number of players.

[Iqbal, 22] introduces the technology of modelling with digital twins as a copy of their physical twins and deals with ethical challenges in medical applications.

[Groves, 22] offers a proposal for the use of an algorithmic impact assessment for data access in a healthcare context. [Baumann, 23] highlights group fairness and actuarial fairness for groups with polygenetic risk.

[Weber, 24] uses the three databases PubMed, SOCAB, and PsycINFO for evaluating six leading tools for measuring patients' trust in their physicians: the Trust in Physician Scale and its various versions, the Wake Forest Physician Trust Scale and its light version, the Health Care Relationship Trust Scale and its refinement, the Trust in Oncologist Scale developed and validated in non-US populations, the Trust in Health Care Providers Scale, and the Trust in My Doctor Scale. Ten dimensions were examined to determine trust: fidelity, professional communication and interpersonal competence in care, honesty, confidentiality, global trust, behavioural trust, fairness, and system trust and accountability. Interpersonal competence and fairness were found to be dimensions that merit further investigation.

Addressing genetic discrimination in social life based on polygenetic risk scores, [Yanes, 24] recommends adequate consideration and care of asymptomatic individuals and their relatives as a result of actual or suspected genetic differences or traits.

Trust in individuals, groups, institutions, societal and scientific progress, privacy, and security. [Ruiz-Martinez, 09] presents a new fair non-repudiation protocol for secure negotiation and contract signing. [Tran, 20] discusses fairness issues in recommender systems, consensus perception, and satisfaction of group members about group recommendations. [Witten, 08] highlights how people use search engines and identify issues of bias, privacy, and personalization.

Fairness in Learning and Teaching. [Lang, 2008] complains that professional and standardization organizations do not consistently use the agreed terminologies and notes: The National Council for Accreditation of Teacher Education NCATE fails to assure the quality of institutional evaluative decisions regarding the relevant standards. Instead of 'validity' and 'reliability', NCATE substitutes 'accuracy' and 'consistency'. NCATE uses the accepted terms of 'fairness' and 'avoidance of bias'. But it confuses them with each other and with validity and reliability.

[Baniasadi, 23] considers components of a fair classroom assessment and identifies 7 themes and 39 sub-themes, obtained in the form of *educational fairness, interactional fairness, procedural fairness, distributive fairness, egalitarian fair assessment, equitable fair assessment*, and the comprehensive notion of validity and reliability. Validity reflects the accuracy of the allocations; reliability is defined as the similarity of the assessment results for a student at different times or by different evaluators.

Fairness in Financial Services. [Devlin, 14] notes that fairness is a complex, multidimensional concept that originates in the theory of justice derived from theories of equity and social exchange. The author discusses the concepts of procedural,

distributive, and interactional fairness and considers their key elements. He derived a comprehensive and robust, multidimensional measure of perceptions of fairness.

After evaluating the thematic orientation and the keywords of the analysed literature, we note the following areas in which various types of fairness and their measures play a role. This gives us the opportunity to cite and summarize the findings of our literature analysis in two tables.

Source	Fairness Context	Short Abstract
Fairness issues, current approaches, and challenges [Jui, 24] O	Taxonomy of ML fairness issues and criteria in various contexts	State-of-the-art research on fairness issues in AI; future directions in ML and AI fairness
Systems with moral and fairness issues [Linardatos, 2021] O	Healthcare, automation, ML, counterfactual discourse, social classes, unequal access	Overview of relevant literature on fairness and explainable AI
Systems/processes: design, models and simulation (Digital twins) [Auer, 09] A	Methodologies & technologies, dimensions, quality criteria, metrics: reliability, accuracy, performance, etc.	Prognosis system for optimizing patient-specific preoperative surgical planning for the human skeletal system
Ethics of Digital Twins in Medicine [Iqbal, 22] A, E	Ethical, legal and societal implications of digital health technologies (DHT)	Conflicts of DHT with ethical principles, including autonomy, benevolence, fairness and justice
Comprehensive taxonomy of ethical and social risks associated to large-scaled language models [Weidinger, 22] B	The paper identifies twenty-one risks in LLMs, drawing on literature from computer science, linguistics, and the social sciences: Taxonomy of six risk areas	1. Discrimination, hate speech and Exclusion, 2. Information Hazards, 3. Misinformation Harms, 4. Malicious Uses, 5. HCI Harms, 6. Environmental and Socioeconomic harms
Fairness and bias in AI: Sources, Impacts, Mitigation Strategies (MS) [Ferrera, 23] B	Data- and repository, model-based, algorithmic, decision, interaction-based fairness, various classifiers	MS related to AI bias: pre- and post-processing, careful model selection, accountable, explainable and comprehensible AI
Sources of Risk (SoR) of AI Systems [Steimers, 22] B	SoR that can influence the trustworthiness of an AI system, reliability, robustness	Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI
Fairness in AI [Dominguez, 24] B	Foundation and large language models, generative AI	14 categories of risks and harms and their individual, social, and biospheric impacts
Assessing the fairness of risk score models [Petersen, 23] C	Fairness of risk-based resource prioritization, i.e., a ranking of subjects based purely on predicted risks, will often be unfair	The fairness of risk score models should be evaluated independently of any subsequent decision-making processes. It is a function of the EV they provide to different groups via a measure

Fairness and quality algorithmic decision-making system (ex. Citizen Score) [Zweig, 18] D, O	Decision-making, classification; evaluates a person's civic behaviour, economic and professional status	Fairness measures can be incompatible with each other in decisions on the granting of credits and public assistance, access to educational opportunities and professions, or insurance conditions.
Northpoint Correctional Offender Management Profiling for Alternative Sanctions validated assessment [Ráz, 22] D	COMPAS: Purpose of public safety pretrial risk assessment (PSPRA), uses decision algorithms to assess recidivism risk	Includes two risk models, one for general offenses and one for crimes and violent crimes, data quality and transparency issues
Organizational Justice in Care Services Creation and Validation of a Measure Toward the Patient [Pérez-Arechaederra, 14] E	Quality criteria of the measure were tested in two sample contexts	Justice dimensions: <i>distributive</i> with equality, equity, and need; <i>procedural</i> with consistency; <i>interactional</i> : respect, education; <i>informational</i> : appropriate, right, sufficient, sincere
Predictably unequal [Paulus, 20] E	Ways to diagnose and remedy algorithmic bias	Framework for valuation of clinical prediction models
Affirmative action in healthcare resource allocation [Zohny, 22] E	Rationale and justifications for using prioritization policies, ethical considerations	Role of race in education, employment in a healthcare setting, applied to COVID-19 pandemic
Constrained fairness [Goethals, 24] O, E	Allocation of scarce resources in healthcare	Concept of resource-constrained Fairness-fair machine learning
Fairness in genetic testing and counseling [Nelson, 19] E	Discriminatory accuracy of RA tools for BRCA1/2 mutations, benefits and harms of RA, genetic counselling and testing, and risk-reducing interventions	Other relevant adverse effects of genetic tests and counselling, such as genetic discrimination and insurability, were not investigated
Measuring trust in one's physician [Weber, 24] E	Search of three databases provided insight into the status of six trust-in-physician measurement tools with known quality criteria	Ten dimensions of trust are identified: fidelity, technical, communicative and interpersonal competence in care, honesty, confidentiality, global, behavioural trust, fairness, and system trust and accountability
Uncertainty quantification in medical image analysis [Huang, 24] E	Paper deals with fields of ML and clinical practice, improves the fairness of the overall healthcare system by combining multiple sources	The paper recommends that researchers consider task-dependent clinical expectations/requirements when selecting assessment criteria for quantifying uncertainty

	of information with uncertainty.	to ensure the fairness and relevance of the assessment criteria.
Machine learning for healthcare—from development to deployment and from models to data [Zhang, 22] B, E	Data shifts and model deterioration can occur when models are deployed on patients with gender, racial or socioeconomic backgrounds	Using non-additional representative or insufficient diversity in the training datasets, underlying limitations of ML models can propagate existing healthcare biases on a large scale, inadequate generalization of model outputs to different patient populations
AI in Healthcare [Schönberger, 19] B, E	Fairness and discrimination in a healthcare context	Developers include policy constraints around PA like gender, age or race to avoid unfair outcomes without exposing them to the risk of legal actions
Foundation metrics in healthcare [Abbasian, 24] B, E	Evaluation of impartiality and equitable performance of healthcare chatbots	Ethical implications of chatbots using fairness metrics biases across demographic users
Actuarial group fairness for groups with polygenetic risk [Yanes, 24, Baumann, 23] C, E	Adequate consideration and care of asymptomatic polygenetic risk as a result of actual or suspected genetic differences or traits	Addressing genetic discrimination in social life based on polygenetic risk scores of individuals and their relatives
Capitation uncertainty quantification in medical image analysis care fee banding [Busby, 18] C, F	Aspects of reliability and validity of an online tool	Investigates quality criteria of Denplan/Previser Patient Assessment capitation fee code guidance through a population study
Fairness in Classroom Assessment [Baniyadi, 23] G	Authors consider components of a fair classroom assessment and identify seven themes and 39 sub-themes	Educational, interactional, procedural, distributive fairness, egalitarian, equitable fair assessment and the comprehensive notion of validity and reliability
Perceptions of Fair Treatment in Financial Services [Devlin, 14] H	Development, Validation and Application of a Fairness Measurement Scale	Concepts of procedural, distributive, and interactional fairness with their key elements. Paper derives a comprehensive and robust multidimensional measure of perceptions of fairness
ACM conference on Fairness, Accountability & Transparency [FAccT, xx] O, ALL	Multidisciplinary research program in computational systems	Computer science, statistics, law, social sciences, humanities, policy

Table 1: Fairness in various contexts

4.2 Fairness Measures from the Perspective of the Concerned Sciences

Source	Kind of Measurement	Short abstract
[Chen, 23] O	Overview on widely used fairness metrics	The paper explains the concepts of fairness in AI systems and explores strategies to reduce various types of biases
[Ferrera, 23] O	Measurement bias occurs when the data collection or measurement systematically over- or under-represents certain groups	Fairness can be achieved through methods such as similarity-based or distance-based measures
[Caton, 24] O, B	Relevant research with the aim of making ML fairer	A discussion of fairness in binary classification, regression, recommender systems, and unsupervised learning is provided
[Dominguez, 24] O, B	For legal, political, organizational or actuarial purposes, risk is generally addressed through quantifiable measures and predictive models of potential negative or harmful events	The detriments of foundation models are often difficult to track and measure - and this affects the ability to coherently balance benefits and detriments
[Mitchell, 21] O, C	Prediction measures, equal decision measures, measurement error	A compact reference guide to the decisions, assumptions and fairness considerations for prediction-based decision-making
[Lang, 08] O, G	Accuracy vs. Validity, Consistency vs. Reliability, and Fairness vs. Absence of Bias in educational measurement	Authors use scholarly work and measurement standards as a basis for differentiating and explaining the terms, in contrast to the use of terminology by the National Council for Accreditation of Teacher Education
[Auer, 09] A	Reliability along with their quality criteria, requirements, attributes and metrics	Multimodal presentation of heterogeneous data, uncertainty in outcome and decision-making need fairness assessment through the whole process
[Weidinger, 22] B	Explainable and interpretable language models (LM) facilitate fairness measurement	The authors propose a comprehensive taxonomy to structure the range of potential ethical and social risks associated with large-scale LMs
[Padh, 21] C	Fairness in classification with a model-agnostic multi-objective algorithm	A novel relaxation of the fairness measure integrated into the proposed multi-objective algorithm results in fair algorithms that have a lower loss of accuracy than the previous ones
[Baumann, 23] C	Group fairness, actuarial fairness for groups avoiding unfair and discriminatory premium systems	The paper maps group fairness criteria, sufficiency or well-calibration to the context of private insurance to avoid systematic unfairness elicited by personal risk

[Bushby, 18] C, E	Healthcare through capitation payments	Valid and reliable protocols can be developed to support risk-based banding-health status measured by the Oral Health Score Component of Denplan Previser Patient Assessment
[Nelson, 19] E	Adverse effects of pre-test genetic counselling: the outcome measures were designed to indicate benefits or harms	Thirteen general risk models are assessed to review evidence on their benefits and harms. Short-term measures of (health) anxiety, depression, distress, uncertainty, and quality of life were similar between testing groups
[Yanes, 24] E, C	International measures to address genetic discrimination in insurance are presented using genome-wide association studies (GWAS)	Polygenetic scores provide an estimate of the genetic liability to health conditions and are calculated based on the impact of multiple disease-associated common genetic variants derived from GWAS
[Anderson, 25] E, C	Overview of individual fairness (IF) metrics	IF metrics, mitigation methods, IF versus group fairness, applications in healthcare
[Pérez-Arechaederra, 14] E, F	Perceived organizational justice OJ in care services (PJustCS): Creation and multi-sample validation of a measure via Confirmatory Factor Analysis	The English and Spanish versions' validation showed expected positive relations of OJ with patients' satisfaction, trust in clinicians and global perceived justice
[Weber, 24]. E, F	Measuring trust in one's physician: highlighting different measures with varied dimensions and indicators Social fairness	Two reviewers screened preselected studies and identified six key measurement tools and ten dimensions of trust. A comparative analysis of indicators/dimensions revealed some discrepancies.
[Zhang, 22] F	GANs are among the most exciting innovations in the area of deep learning in the last decade. They offer the opportunity to generate large amounts of synthetic yet realistic data	The evaluation of the performance of Generative adversarial networks (GANs) is hindered by the lack of efficient and robust metrics when it comes to assessing, comparing and controlling the quality of synthetic data.
[Groves, 22] E, F	Algorithmic impact assessment (AIA) in healthcare measures for risk and quality	Testing and evaluating AIA approaches helps to build a responsive and robust evaluation system, which helps to develop further AIAs by providing a range of case studies and demonstrating how particular resources and expertise could be deployed
[Devlin, 14] H	Fair Treatment in Financial Services: Development, Validation and Application	Authors provide a comprehensive measurement scale with three dimensions and seven sub-dimensions to encapsulate fully consumers' perceptions of fair treatment.

	of a Fairness Measurement Scale	
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Table 2: Fairness assessment, quality of measurement

The next section will present examples of medical tools for calculating disease risks and examine their fairness. The aim is to develop a score-based bias metric to guarantee fairness in risk assessment online tools.

5 Case Study on Fairness in the Use of Medical Tools

Fairness in physical and digital healthcare is related to a modern form of the Hippocratic Oath, which the World Medical Association has published in various versions, most recently in its Geneva Declaration of May 31, 2024.: “As a member of the medical profession... I will not permit considerations of age, disease or disability, creed, ethnic origin, gender, nationality, political affiliation, race, sexual orientation, social standing, or any other factor to intervene between my duty and my patient...” [WMA, 24].

Biases in the healthcare tools, digital models of diagnostics, risk prevention, and received treatments concern content, i.e., data, algorithms, and knowledge creation using AI and ML, patient cohorts, medical experts, and their interaction and collaboration.

Figure 4: The continuous method WPOAG for estimating the 5-year risk R of developing POAG $R = 1 - 0.911^{exp(0.2792 \cdot ((age-56)/12 + (IOP-25)/3) + 0.75566 \cdot (573-CCT)/42 + 0.6262 \cdot ((PSD-1.9) + 10(VCD-3.9)/3.5)}$

Risk Calculator	Scientific study basis: Ocular Hypertension Treatment Study (OHTS) [Karmel, 24] and the European Glaucoma Prevention Study (EGPS)
Content dedication and users	5-year risk that an individual with ocular hypertension will develop POAG; clinicians and patients [Risk Calculators, 24]
Scientific basis	DOI: 10.1016/j.ophta.2006.08.031–Validated prediction model for the development of POAG in individuals with ocular hypertension
Information needed for use	1) Age (y) 2) Vertical cup/disc ratio (VCD) by contour 3) Intraocular pressure (IOP, mmHg) 4) Central Corneal Thickness (CCT, mm) 5) PSD Visual field pattern standard deviation (PSD, dB) and other parameters as (corrected Octopus) loss variance (OLV, dB)–IOP (3 meas.) per eye using

	Goldmann applanation tonometry), CCT using an ultrasound pachymeter (3 meas. per eye), PSD using any of the following (2 meas. per eye), Humphrey full threshold, SITA standard 30-2 or 24-2, LV from Octopus 32-2
Methods	For the Continuous Method enter actual data for the patient's eyes; for the Point System select the range for the patient's age and average of the multiple meas.
Results	Both methods give similar but not identical results.
Limitations and cautions	There is no guarantee that the predicted risk is accurate for individual patients. It is not clear whether these models predict progression of an established disease.
Parameter ranges	$30y \leq a \leq 80y$; IOP range 20–32 mm Hg; CCT 475–658 microns; VCD 0–0.8; PSD 0.5–3.0 dB
About	Information for participants—ocular hypertension and glaucoma—POAG
Copyright: WU 2006	The predictions derived using these methods are designed to aid, but not to replace, clinical judgment.
Department of Ophthalmology & Visual Sciences, Washington University School of Medicine	
OHTS-EGPS GLAUCOMA PREDICTOR, version 2006.1; Washington University	

In a recent work [Luther, 22], we presented online tools that calculate the individual and familial risk for the occurrence of pathogenic variants in BRCA1 (Breast Cancer gene) or BRCA2 genes with impact on early breast (BC) and ovarian cancer (OC) disease, and for estimating the 5-year risk that an individual with ocular hypertension will develop Primary Open Angle Glaucoma (POAG), the leading global cause of irreversible blindness, the angle between the iris and cornea remains open, and drainage does not work properly [Auer, 21, Luther, 22, WHO, 23, Harutyunyan, 24].

The forms collect information about the individuals, their specific disease patterns, medical examination results, and the lifestyle of the proband and his/her relatives. Data and model quality and cross-cutting issues such as uncertainty and usability, and fairness are currently addressed in the context of work in which the authors are involved. Finally, important requirements for online risk prediction tools are formulated, also considering aspects of fairness. The risk of developing glaucoma disease is summarized in Figure 4. The tool uses a log-log regression model that cannot be easily adapted to specific cohorts or ethnicities. In this respect, the reference to possible errors in the risk results is justified, but not conclusive for the groups concerned. The modelling and result generation, the theoretical foundations, the technologies and architectures used are described in comparison with existing tools and validated according to international quality criteria and metrics. To this end, it is necessary to follow the test and control subject groups at least over the period of prediction, but preferably over a longer period, and to adapt the results for other test subject groups and further developed investigation methods, which particularly concern progress in the clarification of the genetic impact [Laroche,22, Luther, 22, Owens, 19, Shaw, 21].

Fairness also means that subgroups in the cohort that have special additional or unique characteristics, whose numbers result in a higher uncertainty factor or require special treatment methods, are not disfavoured. Validated lower and upper bounds are specified for the risk classes, a standard of care guaranteed.

The patient's treatment and the use of suitable technologies are continuously monitored by a panel of experts from the time of initial diagnosis and adjusted accordingly if new insights become available.

In general, it can be said that these requirements are met in the BRCA and glaucoma risk tools under consideration, but with the following restriction. The online form presented to the patient is only used to collect their data and assign them to a risk group. It is usually provided with instructions on how to use it, how to interpret the results, information on advice centres and their services and on version development, the disclaimer, and accompanying scientific literature [AAoO, 19, Risk calculators, 24].

In addition, the tools are validated in scientific (meta-)studies and compared or critically examined in terms of modelling, algorithms and accuracy, as well as applicability for different population groups and treatment periods. In this respect, they are useful for the layperson if medical or nursing expertise can be directly involved [Amir, 10, Kass, 21, Risk Calculators, 24, Laroche, 22, Tham, 21].

[Kuchenbaecker, 17] examines some selection and survival biases and their reasons. [Kass, 21] aimed to determine the cumulative incidence and severity of POAG after 20 years of follow-up among participants in the OHT study.

To determine whether bias occurred in re-participation, the authors compared participants who re-enrolled by randomization group and by baseline clinical and demographic data with those who did not re-enrol.

5.1 Score-Based Bias Metric to Guarantee Fairness in Risk Assessment Tools

We would like to derive some minimum requirements [Risk calculators, 24] as a score-based bias metric with a range of 0–15pts. Certainly, the fairness measure presented is just one of many other quality metrics. On the other hand, the proposed fairness score-based metric can be easily adapted to new developments and medical findings and the growing importance of individual genetic disposition without losing comparability with older versions.

Score-Based Bias Metric

- Risk not sufficiently specified, model for assessing the risk factors and calculating the overall risk or allocation to risk classes invalid or inaccurate → exit
- General information: Adequate information about the system purpose, the target groups, patients and their diseases, disease-related genetic variants, doctors, medical staff, experts, their roles, tasks, and the handling of the output results is needed, FAQ, knowledge base, about, etc. (1 pt.)
- Risk factors: Comprehensible and fair information must be available for each particular question: What kind of information and over what period is expected about the individual's demographics, lifestyle, health status, prior examination results, family disease history, and genetic predisposition? (2 pts.)
- Assignment to risk classes: Depending on the disease pattern, examination outcomes, and patients' own medical samples (e.g., biomarkers), and using transparent risk metrics, patients are assigned to a risk class that is clearly described. If terms such as "high risk," "moderate risk," "low risk," etc. are used, transition classes should be provided to avoid assigning similar individuals to dissimilar classes and to include the impact of epistemic uncertainty or missing data. The assignments to risk classes made with the help of the risk model are validated

with selected patient groups over a longer period of time in accordance with international quality standards (2 pts.)

- Risk model includes risk factors for special groups (1 pt.)
- Assistance: Questionnaires could be completed in a collaborative manner by patients and doctors (1 pt.)
- Data handling: Data and results must also be at disposal over a longer period of time; cross-cutting requirements such as data protection, privacy, and security are respected (2 pts.)
- Expert assistance: Involvement of treating doctor; experts should be given references to relevant literature on data, models, and algorithms, validation, and follow-up (2 pts.)
- Result consequences: Outcomes should be designed in such a way that users are provided with counselling and help services over an appropriate period of time depending on their allocation to a risk class and about the effects of various sources of uncertainty (3 pts.)
- Arbitration boards and mediation procedures in the case of disputes are available (1 pt.)

5.2 Point-Based Risk Calculator Examples Tools

In this section, we examine and classify medical risk tools in terms of their fairness. It turns out that tools with point scores arbitrarily assign patients with very similar health parameters to different risk classes and are therefore rated worse than tools with a continuous risk assessment function. The use of additional overlap risk classes can remedy this shortcoming.

1) Score-based Laroche Glaucoma Calculator [Laroche, 22]

Patient 50/51y, 1/2 pts. Mean IOP 18/19 2/3 pts. CCT 499/500 1/2 pts. → 4/7 pts. “Low/high risk”. Inaccurate model, since small changes in data result in a change in the risk class: the tool should provide an intermediate class for these cases.

2) WPOAG point system risk calculator (<https://ohts.wustl.edu/risk/>): patient 64/65y, mean IOP 24 mmHg, CCT 550, mean VCD 0.4, PSD 2.4 results in 12/13 pts. “intermediate /high risk”.

In general, continuous risk models are preferable to point-based models, as the latter may lead to unfair allocations.

3) In a recent paper [Luther, 22], Validation of Risk Assessment Models for Breast and Ovarian Cancer-Related Gene Variants, algorithmic fairness was achieved for two risk metrics that provide mutual statements about their suitability and about quality criteria such as performance, accuracy, and consistency for the risk models, genetic counselling tools, and comparative surveys. The universal metrics reproduce the mean probability of a BRCA1/2 mutation determined in five large studies with cohorts from different ethnicities and risk classes, suggesting their suitability for further studies as well. Firstly, the study results were correctly calibrated, and secondly, the proposed metrics are universally applicable.

The models presented in [Luther, 22, p. 112] for calculating the risk probabilities are based on the DST, which introduces basic probability assignments with masses m for the individual disease variants and uses their combined occurrences to calculate an overall risk. DST provides an explicit method that is very flexible and always comprehensible, thanks to further basic probability assignments (BPAs) with additional

weights and the inclusion of uncertainty via interval arithmetic. In addition, BPAs for different patient groups, such as patients and their relatives, can also be combined using Dempster's rule. Further fields of application for DST are regression and prediction.

4) At this point, however, it must be mentioned that [CanRisk, 24] provides a very sophisticated tool that is aimed at healthcare professionals. It enables them to calculate an individual's future risks of developing breast and ovarian cancer using cancer family history, genetic and other risk factors, as well as mutation carrier probabilities in breast and ovarian cancer susceptibility genes. The tool is based on the current version 6 of the *Boadicea model*, which is presented, for example, in [Lee, 18]. Here, the fairness measure must be adjusted accordingly, since when used by professionals alone, communication between patient and doctor is usually downstream, and direct use of the tool by patients without the doctor's involvement is not intended.

6 Conclusion and Further Work

An aging population requires access to equitable medical care and trust in medical services, doctors, and nursing staff. The widespread adoption of online advice, prevention, and risk prediction tools makes it imperative to evaluate reliability, validity, and fairness through metrics. Changes and tightening in the definition of risk classes over the past 20 years, advances in imaging techniques and reporting systems, gene panel testing, and use of related genomic and biomarkers have a major impact on the models and algorithms underlying Breast and Ovarian Cancer or Glaucoma Risk Calculators.

Mixed gender and ethnicities in cohorts, lack of data on patients, their disease and family histories, and different standards in digital examinations and polygenic tests performed may lead to highly variable results and non-comparability of risk calculators and their results because of epistemic uncertainty, while the authors cited in the references focus mainly on aleatory uncertainty. A particular challenge is that to this day, there are practically no integrated online tools and multimodal interfaces that meet all the requirements regarding usability, data handling, model construction and classification algorithms, general information about risk factors and classes, expert assistance, result consequences, arbitration boards, and mediation. There is still no consistent consideration of fairness issues like general algorithmic metrics for explainable AI-based software [Shaw, 21, Tham, 14, Tirendi, 23, Topouzis, 21, Wang, 22, Zukerman, 21]. Further work concerns standardizing the development of evaluation frameworks for assessing fairness and biases in medical risk tools, introducing comprehensible criteria catalogues for reliable fairness analytics, and applying them to known risk prediction online software in analogy to the approach in [Weyers, 19] dealing with visual analytics. A further improvement could be to introduce weights into a DST-inspired individual fairness score metric according to their availability of resources and the effort required. In a forthcoming article, we will examine concepts that can be summarized under the overarching term of meta-fairness.

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